

Discrepancy between Clinical Manifestations and Histopathological Features in Borderline Borderline Leprosy

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ABSTRACT Leprosy is a chronic and progressive granulomatous disease that primarily affects the skin and peripheral nervous system caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. If left unrecognized, the infection can cause permanent nerve damage and disability. The mid-borderline type is the most unstable type, where clinical presentation depends on the patient's immune response and may result in a broad spectrum of symptoms. ROM (rifampicin, ofloxacin, minocycline) is second-line therapy for leprosy recommended by WHO for patients who have contraindications or reject MDT administration. A case of a 49-year-old male patient was reported with an ulcer on the right hand, peeling skin on both hands, legs, accompanied with erythematous nodules and plaque, and hyperpigmented macules almost all over the body. Skin all over body was painful and followed with fever. Clinical manifestation is mimicking borderline lepromatous and severe leprosy reaction, but histopathology result supports Borderline borderline leprosy. The patient was treated with Rifampicin, Ofloxacin, Minoksiklin (ROM) and Prednisone, which resulted in significant clinical improvement.

KEYWORDS Borderline borderline, Leprosy, ROM

Introduction

Leprosy is a chronic granulomatous infection caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*, which involves the skin and nerves. It is an intracellular pathogen that primarily infects macrophages and Schwann cells, multiplies in muscle and vascular endothelium, and can infect other tissues such as the eyes and testicles. [1, 2].

According to WHO, the diagnosis of leprosy is based on clinical signs and symptoms. In endemic areas, a person is diagnosed with leprosy if there is one of the cardinal signs such as hypopigmented or erythematous skin lesions accompanied by loss of sensation, affects peripheral nerves characterized by

nerve thickening and sensory loss, with positive slit skin smear. [3]

In most patients, skin lesions were the primary clinical manifestations, and various skin lesions appear during the course of the disease. This is a significant challenge for dermatologists to distinguish between leprosy and other conditions of skin disorders. [1]

The difference between clinical manifestations and histopathological examination often occurs, especially in Mid-borderline (BB) leprosy patients. [4] This can be caused by several factors such as changes in the host's immune system, the location of sampling, the age of lesion, side of lesion, and depth of sample taken. The changes in the histopathological picture are based on the status of the host immune system, so that other investigation such as the slit skin smear and Fite Faraco staining are needed, which were the most appropriate examination to look for the presence of leprosy bacilli. [4, 5] Based on the WHO classification in 1988, if the bacterial index (IB) is 0, then the diagnosis leads to paucibacillary (PB) leprosy while the IB is +1 or more leads to the multibacillary (MB) leprosy. [6]

We reported a case of a 49 years old, male, with desquamation on both hands and feet, accompanied by hyperpigmented

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Figure 1: Multiple hyperpigmented macules topped with an ulcer, blackish crust over the face (A), abdomen (B), and (C) superior extremities.

Figure 2: Histopathological examination 2.a. Epidermal atrophy (red arrow) and granuloma within dermal layer (black arrow) 10x magnification 2.b. Granuloma consist of histiocytic foamy macrophages 40x magnification

Figure 3: Fite Faraco staining found no bacilli.

macules and erythematous nodules, on both hands, feet, face and back associated with pain. The clinical manifestations lead to a leprosy reaction, but histopathological results did not support this. Patients treated with ROM and Prednisone showed clinical improvement.

Case Report

A 49-year-old male patient came to the Emergency Department of Dr Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital with a chief complaint of desquamation on both hands and feet for almost two weeks. Initially, three months ago there was a water-filled bubble on the right arm which ruptured and resulting in a wound. Also, there were thickened and erythematous nodules on both thighs and face; and hyperpigmented macules on both hands and feet. The patient also complained of fever and joint pain in both hands and feet that led to mobility restriction. The patient's skin was very painful on palpation. There was a weight loss for a total of 10 kg in the last three months. There was a history of the

same previous illness, where the patient received intravenous methylprednisolone treatment but was not diagnosed as leprosy. History of drug and food allergy was denied. History of diabetes mellitus was also denied. There was no history of family members who suffered from the same illness.

The results of the physical examination showed that the patient looked moderately ill, *compos mentis*, with vital signs within normal limits. On dermatological examination multiple erythematous nodules were noted on the face; ulcers, erosions, and crusts over the superior extremities; plaques, nodules, erythematous macules and hyperpigmented macules over the posterior trunk, superior extremities and inferior, and erythematous macules on the abdomen.

The sensibility examination of the lesions on the posterior trunk, both superior extremities from the brachial to the manus region, and on the lower third of both lower extremities showed hypoesthesia. Also, the left ulnar nerve enlargement nerve was found. No abnormalities in the facial nerve, greater auricular nerve, or common peroneal nerve were found. The muscle strength of all four extremities were all within normal limits.

On complete blood examination, leukocytosis $33.4 \times 10^3 / \text{uL}$ anemia 9.3 gr / dl, and hypoalbuminemia 2.5 g / L were found. Skin smear examination showed positive acid-fast bacilli on the right ear (3+), left ear (3+), and skin lesions (1+) with a morphological Index (MI) of 3 and bacterial Index (BI) of 5%. Histopathological examination showed atrophic epidermis with no epidermal necrosis. Granulomas along the adnexa consisting of foamed histiocytic cells mixed with lymphocytes were found in the dermis. Fite Faraco staining difficult to find any bacilli. There were no bacilli found within the granuloma or in the blood vessels. Histopathological results supported the diagnosis of mid-borderline leprosy.

Based on the history, physical examination and supporting examinations, the patient was diagnosed with multibacillary leprosy and treated with Rifampicin 600 mg, Ofloxacin 400 mg, Minocycline 100 mg, three times a week for a total of 36 weeks. Also, the patient was given vitamin B complex q.d, Ranitidine tablet t.i.d, Mefenamic acid t.i.d and Prednisone 30 mg/day orally, with 20 mg given in the morning and 10 mg in the afternoon. The wound was compressed with normal saline dressing for 5-10 minutes in the morning and evening.

Discussion

Leprosy can occur at any age, but most commonly found in the age of 20-30 years with men more frequently affected than women with a ratio of 2:1. [7] This was also found in our patient.

The diagnosis of leprosy can be established by finding one out of three cardinal signs, including hypopigmented or erythematous macules associated with loss of sensation, thickening of the peripheral nerves with nerve involvement, and AFB on bacteriological examination. This patient fulfils three cardinal signs in establishing a diagnosis of leprosy. According to Ridley Jopling's classification, leprosy is divided into five groups based on the immunological response of the patient, where the type of tuberculoid (TT) and lepromatous type (LL) were a stable polar pole. Borderline type (BB) is the most unstable type because patients in this group can be quickly downgraded to LL type if not treated. [1] BB type leprosy showed erythematous lesions in the form of polymorphic plaques that can be in the form of punched out and infiltrating plaques with undefined borders. Lesions are usually symmetrical and tend to be polymorphic. [8] These polymorphic lesions are initially small in number but rapidly

spread throughout the body. In addition, there were papules and nodules with an asymmetrical distribution of lesions, where some nodules appear more concave in the middle and annular in shape, the lesions in the middle often appear normal with edges in the infiltrates more clearly than the outer edges and some plaques can be shaped like punched out lesions resemble swiss cheese appearance. Multiple lesions usually lead to symmetrical distribution. Lesions on the face are usually infiltrated with nodules in around the ear and chin. Nerve damage varies in borderline type of leprosy. [1, 2] In BL type leprosy, few skin lesions can spread rapidly throughout the body. Other lesions in the form of papules and nodules become apparent even though they are small, where the distribution is almost symmetrical. [1] Lesions are found in the form of macules, plaques and erythema nodules, ulcers, erosions, crusts, hyperpigmented macules with atrophic lesions. This clinical picture is by borderline lepromatous leprosy or leprosy reaction. Several studies of leprosy patients have shown a significant difference between bacteriological and immunological status compared to clinical diagnosis. The incompatibility of clinical manifestations and histopathological features in leprosy patients often occurs especially in BB-type leprosy, because of its unstable and polar nature, where these types are easily experienced downgrading or upgrading. This is because the immune response is still changing according to the course of MH disease and the patient's immunological status. The taking of inadequate biopsy specimens can cause the discordance of clinical and histopathological manifestations. Factors including the depth in taking biopsy sampling, selection of lesions, how to store specimens and the time interval of sampling with the staining carried out in effect the outcome result. Also, the MH type BB spectrum is relatively easy to shift and takes place in a short time so that the diagnosis becomes less precise. [4, 5]

The histopathological examination found epidermal atrophy, in the dermal layer there is granuloma with macrophages. The granuloma consists of histiocytic foamy cells mixed with few lymphocytes. Histopathological results support the Borderline Borderline leprosy. BB leprosy histology is almost similar to BL type where a mixture of epithelioid cells and macrophages forms granulomas. Lymphocytes were small but scattered; multinuclear giant cells were not found, where these characteristics can distinguish them from BT types. [8]

Erythematous nodules associated with pain, warmth, with constitutional symptoms such as malaise, pain and a history of fever a few days earlier can be found in patients with leprosy reactions. [9, 10] Histopathological examination showed there is no evidence of neutrophil cell infiltrates, venous endothelial oedema, arterioles, small arteries, and vasculitis mixed with eosinophils which is the characteristic histopathological features of leprosy reactions. [11]

ROM is a choice for patients who reject or have contraindications to multidrug use. [12] A study by Rahman in 2018, slit skin smear became negative on month 12 after given 36 doses of ROM for three months. [13] Villahermosa et al. in 2004, and Lockwood in 2012 compared ROM combination therapy every month for 24 months with MDT MB in MB leprosy patients, found that ROM therapy was safe and effective, did not cause skin pigmentation, and showed improvement in terms of clinical manifestation, bacteriological and histopathology. [14, 15] Study in Senegal evaluating the effectiveness of intermittent ROM therapy in 102 PB patients and 118 MB patients during the first year. Patients tolerated the drug well and had no side ef-

fects. Short-term observations show a decrease in BI and similar clinical regression as seen with WHO MDT administration (PB and MB). [1]

Conclusion

The discrepancy between the clinical manifestations and histopathological findings often occurs especially in borderline leprosy patients because this spectrum is unstable and relatively brief, causing BB cases to be rarely found. Clinical manifestations of BB leprosy can vary and mimic BT, BL, LL, and leprosy reactions. Treating the worst possible case based on the clinical and histopathological features are advised to prevent undertreatment. Consideration of giving MDT and ROM must be based on improvement in clinical, bacteriological and histopathological result to obtain optimal treatment results.

Competing Interests

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References

1. Kumar B, Kumar H. IAL Textbook of Leprosy. Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers (P) Ltd. 2nd edition. 2016.
2. Delphine J, Lee T. Leprosy. In: Goldsmith L, Gilchrist B, Katz S, Paller A, Leffell D, Wolff K, editors. Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine. 2. 8th ed. New York: McGraw Hill Professional; 2012. p. 2253–63.
3. Bhat R, Prakash C. Leprosy: An Overview of Pathophysiology. *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Infectious Diseases*. 2012;2012:6.
4. Arunagirinathan M, Muniswamy V, Sivaraman J. Clinical and Histopathological Correlation in Hansen's Disease. 2016.
5. Manandhar U, Adhikari R, Sayami G. Clinico-histopathological correlation of skin biopsies in leprosy. *Journal of Pathology of Nepal*. 2013;3(6):452-8.
6. WHO. Chemotherapy of leprosy for control programmes: report of a WHO study group Technical Report Series, 675 WHO: Geneva; 1982.
7. Walker S, Withington S, Lockwood D. Leprosy. *Manson's Tropical Infectious Diseases*. 1st ed 2014. p. 506-18.
8. Bryceson A, Pfaltzgraff RE. Leprosy: Churchill Livingstone; 1990.
9. Negera E, Walker SL, Girma S, Doni SN, Tsegaye D, Lambert SM, et al. Clinico-pathological features of erythema nodosum leprosum: A case-control study at ALERT hospital, Ethiopia. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. 2017;11(10):e0006011.

10. Walker SL, Lebas E, Doni SN, Lockwood DN, Lambert SM. The mortality associated with erythema nodosum leprosum in Ethiopia: a retrospective hospital-based study. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*. 2014;8(3):e2690.
11. Massone C, Belachew WA, Schettini A. Histopathology of the lepromatous skin biopsy. *Clinics in dermatology*. 2015;33(1):38-45.
12. Moestopo O, Gunawan H, Dahlan A. Comparison of Effectiveness between Rifampicin Ofloxin-Minocycline Regimen and Multidrug Therapy-World Health Organization in Multibacillary Leprosy Patients. *Althea Medical Journal*. 2017;3(4):661-5.
13. Rahman E, Muchtar S, Tabri F, Wahab S, Adriani A, Seweng A, et al. Evaluation of Interleukin-12 and Interleukin-4 Levels in Multibacillary-type Leprosy Patient 12 Months after Rifampicin Ofloxacin Minocycline Combination Therapy 2018. 1 p.
14. Villahermosa LG, Fajardo Jr TT, Abalos RM, Cellona RV, Balagon MV, Cruz ECD, et al. Parallel assessment of 24 monthly doses of rifampin, ofloxacin, and minocycline versus two years of World Health Organization multi-drug therapy for multi-bacillary leprosy. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene*. 2004;70(2):197-200.
15. Lockwood DN, Cunha MDG. Developing new MDT regimens for MB patients; Time to test ROM 12 month regimens globally. *Leprosy review*. 2012;83(3):241-4.